

A STUDY OF ROLE OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY IN INDIAN EDUCATION
Dr. Rani Somnath Shitole
Shri Shahu Mandir Mahavidyalaya, Pune
Abstract

National Education Policy is a comprehensive framework o guide the development of education in the country. The main aim of new education policy is to develop good human beings, to producing productive and contributing citizens. It is based on flexibility. Learners have choice to select subject as per his/her choice. It provides multidisciplinary and holistic education for a multidisciplinary world. The vision of the new education policy is to develop knowledge, skills, values, spirit, and values among the students which help in supporting responsible commitment to human rights. New education Policy provides an opportunity to brilliant professionals to enter in education sector. It provides dignity, respect, good living standard and autonomy to teacher.

Keywords: *Introduction, Role of new education policy towards the students, Early Childhood Care and Education, Structure of New Education Policy.*

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Introduction:

The National Education Policy was approved by the union cabinet of India on 29th July 2020. K. Kasturrangan, former chairman, ISRO, Bengluru was the chairperson of committee for the draft of National Education Policy. National Education Policy is a comprehensive framework o guide the development of education in the country. This policy is the dynamic policy. The main aim of the new education policy is to face the new challenges in technology, computer, science, social science and other aspects. The main aim of new education policy is to develop good human beings, to producing productive and contributing citizens. It is based on flexibility. Learners have choice to select subject as per his/her choice. It provides multidisciplinary and holistic education for a multidisciplinary world.

It focuses on the development of the students. Following points are included in it.

- To achieving foundational literacy and numeracy.
- To create creativity and critical thinking among the students,
- To improve the role of teacher in learning process.
- To develop students in academic and non academic stage.
- To provide right to select their own path.

Role of new education policy towards the students:

New education policy aim is to provide quality education to students. To give importance to local and global needs of the country, new education policy provide tools for achieving goal. It develops self-confidence, self-knowledge, cooperation and integration among the students. The main aim of new education policy is to provide productive and contributing citizens for building nation. As per the new education policy education institutions provide good physical

facility, learning environment to all students. By providing a high quality education to all the students and help them making India a global knowledge superpower. The vision of the new education policy is to develop knowledge, skills, values, spirit, and values among the students which help in supporting responsible commitment to human rights.

Early Childhood Care and Education:

The main aim of new education policy is that produce access of to all children to participate in education system and shape their knowledge and skill. ECCE is flexible, multi-level play based activity based and inquiry based learning. Its goal is to develop communication skill.

Role of teacher in New Education Policy:

Teacher must be play important role in fundamental reforms in the education system. Teacher is the backbone of the society and it help to develop, shape and guide new generation citizens. New education Policy provides an opportunity to brilliant professionals to enter in education sector. It provides dignity, respect, good living standard and autonomy to teacher. Role of teacher is vital in the development of education in India.

Equitable and Inclusive Education and Learning for all.

Through only education tool we achieve social justice and equality. Every child can get benefit and opportunity to learn. It focuses on reducing social category gap in school education. The Government of India composes a Gender Inclusion Fund for nation building by providing equitable and quality education for all girls and also to transgender students. Transgender students also get access of education.

Restructuring School Curriculum and Pedagogy in a new design:

The curricular and pedagogical structure of school education will be reconfigured to make it responsive. The foundational stage will be for 5 years. The basic aim of 5+3+3+4 structure is to involve students in education process from the age of 3 for better development and overall learning.

Structure of New Education Policy

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